

DISTINGUISHING BETWEEN STRAIN MEASUREMENT PROCEDURES DURING COMPRESSIVE TESTING OF FOAM MATERIALS

Moeen S. Rajput, Magnus Burman and Stefan Hallström

KTH Royal institute of Technology
Department of Aeronautical and Vehicle Engineering
Division of Lightweight Structures
SE 100 44, Stockholm Sweden
Email: mudsra@kth.se

Keywords: Cellular Plastic, Young's Modulus, Test Methods

ABSTRACT

The out-of-plane compressive properties of foam materials are essential for their performance as core material in sandwich structures. Accurate data for these properties are crucial for modeling and analysis of impact response and critical design assessment of e.g. sandwich structures. Current standards differ in specifying how the strains should be measured. When different standard methods are used, significant differences in test results for flatwise compression are obtained. An experimental study of the out-of-plane compressive properties (strength and modulus) of foam materials is conducted, where two types of foams are studied; Rohacell 200 Hero and Divinycell H60. Both are closed cell structured foams used for cores in sandwich materials. A review of established test methodologies is conducted and the test results show that there is a significant difference in strain values measured from the cross head displacement (termed “gross core strain”) and when extensometer directly applied onto the foam (termed “net core strain”). The results are not related to the compliance of the test rig, which is another issue outside the scope of this investigation. The effect of surface priming on the compressive behavior is further investigated followed by digital image correlation (DIC) for detailed recordings of the strain fields.

1 INTRODUCTION

The demand for lightweight structures coupled with high performance requirements has enhanced the use of composite sandwich structures (two stiff composite faces separated by a low density core), in applications where high bending strength to weight ratio is desired [1]. Mechanical properties of sandwich materials depend on the properties of their core and face sheet materials and of their face-core interfaces [2]. Selection of core material is critical in the design of sandwich structures since face-core de-bonding and core crushing are main sources of failure initiation in sandwich structures [3–5]. Sufficient understanding about the extraction of core material properties is thus essential. Several studies have previously investigated compressive properties of sandwich structure [6–10], but no thorough study has been conducted entirely focused on the flatwise compressive properties of foam core materials.

In the present paper, the focus is on measurements of flatwise compressive properties of foam core material using different test methods, not only because it is crucial for the design of sandwich structures, but also vital for accurate modelling and analysis of impact and indentation responses [11,12]. The test procedure for evaluation of the compressive properties of foam materials is studied in detail from the light of existing test standards. Different specimen configurations and tests are studied and analysed, partly with detailed digital image correlation (DIC) analysis. Finally, recommendations for more reliable test results and improvements of the test standards are proposed.

2 METHOD

2.1 Specimen Preparation

In the present study, foam materials are tested in compression, both with and without face sheets. Two different closed-cell foam materials are used in the study, Evonic Rohacell 200 Hero and DIAB Divinycell H60. Both materials represent common classes of structural foams but have different density and cell size as shown in Figure 1. The test specimens are cut to desired size in a band saw and weighed before testing.

Apart from plain foam samples, sandwich specimens are also manufactured using uni-directional (UD) carbon fiber (HTS40-242 g/m²) layers as face sheets, with a stacking sequence of [0]₁₀, providing a laminate thickness of 2.5mm. Only the Rohacell 200 Hero is used in the sandwich specimens. The sandwich panel is produced using vacuum infusion, with Vinylester DION 9102 as resin. The test specimens are machined from the sandwich panel using a band saw with a diamond-coated cutting blade. The manufacturer's data and the test specimen configuration are presented in Table 1 and Table 2 respectively.

Figure 1 Microscopy of Rohacell 200 Hero (left) and Divinycell H60 foam material (right)

Table 1: Manufacturer's data

Material	Foam Nomenclature	Nominal Density [Kg/m ³]	Comp. Strength [MPa]	Comp. Modulus [MPa]
Rohacell 200 Hero	RC-200	205	7.1	180
Divinycell H60	DV-H60	60	0.9	70

Table 2: Specimen configuration

Test configuration	Foam type	Specimen nomenclature	Foam Thickness [mm]	No. of samples	Sample size [mm]
Foam	Rohacell 200 Hero	RC-200	20	5	50x50
	Divinycell H60	DV-H60	50	5	50x50
Primed	Rohacell 200 Hero	P-RC-200	20	5	50x50
	Divinycell H60	P-DV-H60	50	5	50x50
Sandwich	Rohacell 200 Hero	SS-RC200	20	5	30x30

2.2 Test Setup

The tests are performed in universal test machines using load cells as per load level requirements. A detailed description of the test setup, along with instrumentations used, is presented in Table 3. Specimens are placed in between the two rigid (steel) platens, carefully mounted on the fixture, perfectly parallel to each other, in order to avoid uneven stress distribution in the specimens. For the initial guideline, two standard test methods are used, ASTM D1621.10 [13] (equivalent to ISO 844:2009) and ASTM C365/365M-11a [14]. The former standard is specific for the estimation of compressive properties of rigid cellular plastics, whereas the latter is used extensively for the flatwise compressive properties of sandwich cores. In the ASTM standard, strains are recorded by monitoring the crosshead displacement using a displacement measurement device, in order to eliminate compliance of the machine. Whereas, no specific strain measurement recommendation is given in the ISO 844:2009 standard.

A computer system is connected to the test machine for the recording of the force and the crosshead displacement. Two extensometers are used, one measuring displacement between the steel plates (Ext. 1) and one measuring displacement directly onto the specimen (Ext. 2). A typical test setup is shown in Figure 2.

Table 3: Description of the test setup

Material		RC-200, DV-H60
Steel plate dia.	[mm]	80
Test machine	–	Instron 4505
Load Cell	[kN]	100
Sampling frequency	[Hz]	10
Extensometer	–	No.1: Instron 2620-601 (200873) No.2: Instron 2620-601 (205210)
Cross head speed	–	10% of specimen thickness per minute
Testing Condition	–	Temp. 25 °C & RH 47 %

Figure 2: Test Setup

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Foam compression

In the current study the strains are measured using two extensometers;

- Extensometer 1 (Ext.1) measures the true cross-head displacement, and the corresponding strain is denoted “*gross core strain*”.
- Extensometer 2 (Ext.2) measures the displacement directly onto the specimen and the resulting strain is termed “*net core strain*”.

Engineering stress-strain curves from two extensometers are shown in Figure 3, and the calculated compressive modulus is presented in Table 4.

Figure 3: Engineering stress-strain curves under flatwise compression

As seen there is a significant difference between the two strain measurements, resulting in large differences in the evaluated compressive moduli. However, the compressive strength is apparently unaffected by the use of either method, since it does not rely on the strain measurements. The stress-strain curve from the measured gross core strain (Ext.1) shows an initial toe region, which is explained by seating effects at the test initiation. No such behavior is observed when the extensometer is mounted onto the core, i.e. when the net core strain (Ext.2) is measured. These same observations are made for both tested foam materials, irrespective of cell size and density, thereby showing that this variation in strains from the different measurement methods is not material dependent.

Table 4: Compressive modulus comparison from different test methods

Material	In-Plane Size [mm ²]	Compressive modulus				
		Ext.1 [MPa]	Ext.2 [MPa]	Priming		DSP [MPa]
				Ext.1 [MPa]	Ext.2 [MPa]	
RC-200	50x50	277 ±26	405 ±38	279±15	410 ±24	413 ±10
DV-H60	50x50	39 ±10	70 ±8	51 ±7	72 ±9	74 ±12

3.2 Foam surface priming

In the previous section differences in the strain readings are described, where measurements are performed on the core directly or on the loading platens of the test rig. The differences indicate presence of local effects at the loaded surfaces of the core materials. One hypothesis is then that broken cells on the cut surfaces induce relatively higher strains locally. In order to verify that, an experimental series is performed where the top and bottom surfaces of foam material are primed. Vinyl Ester Dion 9102 is used to stabilize the potential open/cut cells, at the both top and bottom surfaces. The test matrix is presented in Table 2, and the resulting stress-strain curves from Ext.1

(*gross core strain*) are shown in Figure 4. The corresponding modulus values are also presented in Table 4.

Figure 4: Gross core strain comparison (primed vs non-primed)

There is no significant difference observed in the modulus value for *gross core strain* of Rohacell 200 Hero material between the primed and non-primed specimens. However for the Divinycell H60 foam, a significant difference in modulus value is observed, i.e. around 20% increase after priming. This difference is believed to come from the difference in core cell size. The H60 has larger cell size (4-5 times) compared to the 200 Hero (see Figure 1), thus the open/cut cells on the H60 surface are more likely to be susceptible to the effects of the priming process, while the resin might not penetrate the smaller cells in the 200 Hero foam up to the same extent. However, there are still significant differences between the net and gross core strains after priming (see Table 4), indicating that, although open/cut cells affect the (compressive modulus) results for foam materials with large cells, it is still not the main source of deviation between the two strain measurements.

3.3 Sandwich configuration

Continuing to investigate the effect of core surface modification and its influence on the strain readings for the gross core strains, the foam is tested as core in a sandwich material. The material specifics are given in section 2.1. The objective here is to eliminate possible local deformation of the foam material due to uneven load introduction at the loaded surfaces. The test matrix is presented in Table 2 and the results are shown in Figure 5.

Figure 5: Engineering stress-strain curves under flatwise compression for the sandwich configuration

The gross core strain result (in Table 4) shows no improvement in compressive modulus compared to other configurations. In fact, it is important to mention here that the gross core strain is still capturing the cross head displacement, which includes the deformation due to face-plate interaction, therefore DIC system is utilized for detailed evaluation.

3.4 Digital Image Correlation (DIC) Analysis

To fully measure and visualize the deformation and strain variation within the foam specimens a full field optical strain measuring system (ARAMIS, GOM mbH) is used for parallel measurements in the current study with the setup shown in Figure 6. The strain measurements from the DIC system are time synchronized with the test machine, thus the stress-strain curve can be extracted directly from the DIC system and correlated with the extensometer results.

The DIC system captures the results at a rate of 1 frame/second, considered to be sufficient for the relatively slow quasi-static compression testing at hand. A comparison of stress-strain curves coming from the DIC and extensometer readings are shown in Figure 7 for the two different foams studied.

Figure 6: DIC setup

Figure 7: Comparison of extensometer and DSP results

The DIC results correspond well with the net core strain results, which further strengthen the conclusion that the cell size is not the main cause of the measurement differences. Instead it is the

appropriate choice of strain gauge length that appears to be the matter of importance, i.e. the net core strain rather than the gross core strain should be used for more reliable readings.

Strain mapping analysis is performed for the sandwich configuration and shown in Figure 8. Local high strains can be seen at the interface of face sheet and load plates, whereas a virtually constant strain through the thickness is visible in the core material. This analysis addresses the higher gross core strain compared to strains obtained from direct measurement of displacement onto the core (net core strain).

Additionally, In case the foam specimens are too thin to allow for net core strain measurements with an extensometer, bonding the test specimen to the load plates would likely eliminate the problems with the gross core strain readings.

Figure 8 Strain mapping analysis for sandwich configuration

4 CONCLUSION

The flatwise compressive properties of foam core materials are investigated using two different gauge lengths for strain measurements, referred to as net and gross strain. Significant differences are observed between measurements using the two different gauge attachments, which in terms of strain measurements lead to different compressive modulus results. The compressive strength is apparently unaffected by the use of method since it does not rely on the strain measurements. Various reasons for the different strain measurements are assessed by use of different specimen configurations and parallel DIC analysis, leading to the conclusion that the net core strain should be measured for accurate readings of the strain and modulus from flatwise compression tests.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

The present work has been performed with support from VINNOVA (Swedish Governmental Agency for Innovation Systems) within the project NFFP6 2013-01132 (DAMTISS).

REFERENCES

1. J.R. Vinson, Sandwich Structures. *Applied Mechanics Reviews*, **54**, 2001, pp. 201–214.
2. Z. Shen, Z. Wang, & J. Yang et al., Characterization of damage resistance and damage tolerance behaviour of composite laminates, *Acta Materiae Compositae Sinica* **21**, 2001, pp. 140–145.
3. A. Shipsha, & D. Zenkert, Compression-after-Impact Strength of Sandwich Panels with Core Crushing Damage, *Applied Composite Materials* **12**, 2005 pp. 149–164.
4. A. Shipsha, S. Hallström, & D. Zenkert, Failure Mechanisms and Modelling of Impact Damage in Sandwich Beams - A 2D Approach: Part I - Experimental Investigation, *Journal of Sandwich Structures and Materials*, **5**, 2003, pp. 7–31.
5. I. Ivañez, C. Santiuste, & S. Sanchez-Saez, FEM analysis of dynamic flexural behaviour of composite sandwich beams with foam core, *Composite Structures*, **92**, 2010, pp. 2285–2291.
6. A.I. Marasco, D.D.R. Cartié, I.K. Partridge, & A. Rezai, Mechanical properties balance in novel Z-pinned sandwich panels: Out-of-plane properties, *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing*, **37**, 2006, pp. 295–302.
7. M. Motuku, U.K. Vaidya, R. Rodgers, & S. Jeelani, Characterization of Static Compressive, Low Velocity Impact and High Strain Rate Impact Response of Foam Core Sandwich Composites: Effect of Foam Core Density and Facesheet Thickness, *13th International Conference on Composite Materials*, 2001.
8. Q.M. Li, R.A.W. Mines, R.S. Birch, The crush behaviour of Rohacell-51WF structural foam, *International Journal of Solids and Structures*, **37**, 2000, pp. 6321–6341.
9. F. Mujika, J. Pujana, M. Olave, On the determination of out-of-plane elastic properties of honeycomb sandwich panels, *Polymer Testing*, **30**, 2011, pp. 222–228.
10. S. Ouellet, D. Cronin, M. Worswick, Compressive response of polymeric foams under quasi-static, medium and high strain rate conditions, *Polymer Testing*, **25**, 2006, pp. 731–743.
11. D. Zenkert, A. Shipsha, & K. Persson, Static indentation and unloading response of sandwich beams, *Composites Part B: Engineering*, **35**, 2004, pp. 511–522.
12. V. Rizov, A. Shipsha, & D. Zenkert, Indentation study of foam core sandwich composite panels, *Composite Structures*, **69**, 2005, pp. 95–102.
13. Technical Standard ASTM D1621-10. Standard Test Method for Compressive Properties of Rigid Cellular Plastics. *ASTM Digital Library*, 2010.
14. Technical Standard ASTM C365/C365M - 11a. Standard Test Method for Flatwise Compressive Properties of Sandwich Cores. *ASTM Digital Library*, 2011.